

Milestone MS12

Integrated phenotypic, genotypic and environmental data

Due date of milestone: 31 / Dec / 2025

Actual achievement date: ...

Work package concerned: WP5

Person in charge of the deliverable (and role in the project): Diego Micheletti

Main author: Diego Micheletti

Additional authors: Michela Troggio, Maria Josè Aranzana

'Milestones' are control points in the action that help to chart progress. They may correspond to the completion of a key deliverables, allowing the next phase of the work to begin or be needed at intermediary points (go-no-go point).

A milestone, contrary to a deliverable, will not be submitted on the EU participant portal but some part of it will be used on the EU portal.

The core of this report (all sections except annexes) should be short (~1 page and a half). Details can be added as annexes.

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Abstract

This report outlines data acquisition and characterization phases for a pan-European environmental modelling and fruit tree genotyping project. A comprehensive environmental dataset comprising 209 variables at a high spatial resolution of 0.025° (approx. 1 km) was aggregated from CHELSA (Karger et al. 2017) and SoilGrids 2.0 (Poggio et al. 2021), covering the region from Europe to Armenia. Concurrently, extensive genotyping campaigns were executed on both *in-situ* and *ex-situ* collections. This included the validation of species purity for approximately 600 *Malus sylvestris* samples via the ThermoFisher Axiom JKI50kMd array, and the characterization of *Pyrus* and *Prunus* populations using SSR markers. While Whole-Genome Sequencing (WGS) has been completed for the *ex-situ* wild Apricot collection (INRAE Bordeaux) While preliminary data on phenotypic traits related to resilience, food and non-food uses, and fruit and leaves 'omics' are already available (MS11), phenotyping efforts regarding resilience and utility traits are currently in progress and will extend along the project. All associated metadata has been successfully centralized in the Breeding Information Management System (BIMS) and the FruitDiv SharePoint.

Karger, D. N., Conrad, O., Böhner, J., Kawohl, T., Kreft, H., Soria-Auza, R. W., ... & Kessler, M. (2017). Climatologies at high resolution for the earth's land surface areas. *Scientific data*, 4(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2017.122>

Poggio, L., de Sousa, L. M., Batjes, N. H., Heuvelink, G. B. M., Kempen, B., Ribeiro, E., and Rossiter, D.: SoilGrids 2.0: producing soil information for the globe with quantified spatial uncertainty, *SOIL*, 7, 217–240, <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-7-217-2021>, 2021.

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1 Background

Understanding how European wild fruit tree species respond to climate pressures, and human influence requires an integrated approach combining environmental, genomic, and phenotypic information. Many wild relatives of cultivated fruit trees (*Malus*, *Pyrus*, *Prunus*) are distributed across highly heterogeneous landscapes, and their adaptive potential remains insufficiently characterised. This limits our ability to design conservation strategies, identify resilient genotypes, and support breeding programmes that rely on wild genetic resources.

One of the hypotheses of the project is that environmental gradients across Europe have shaped the genetic structure, adaptive variation, and phenotypic diversity of wild fruit tree populations, and that these patterns can be detected by combining high-resolution environmental data with genomic and phenotypic datasets of both in-situ and ex-situ material.

To support this objective, the project must assemble a dataset that captures:

- Environmental variation across Europe, using publicly available climate and soil databases (e.g., CHELSA, SoilGrids).
- Genetic diversity of wild and cultivated accessions, through SNP arrays, SSR markers, and whole-genome sequencing.
- Phenotypic traits relevant to adaptation, resilience, and potential uses, collected from ex-situ collections under controlled conditions.
- Metadata and passport information to ensure traceability, interoperability, and integration across partners.

2 Work done and current status

Environmental data

Initial preparatory work focused on data acquisition for environmental modelling. Environmental parameters were successfully downloaded from the CHELSA and SoilGrids databases, resulting in a comprehensive dataset including a total of 209 variables. These variables cover the extent of Europe, stretching eastward to Armenia, which is the furthest sampling location of the project. This comprehensive dataset maintains a high resolution, specifically 0.025° (approximately 1km), ensuring detailed spatial information is available for all analyses.

Genotypic data

Parallel to the environmental data collection, extensive genotyping efforts were conducted on *in-situ* collections. For *in-situ* samples, genotyping was successfully completed for approximately 600 samples of wild *Malus* species, utilising the ThermoFisher Axiom JK150kMd array mainly to determine the species purity of these wild samples. Further genotyping was executed for several *Pyrus* (close to 800 samples) and *Prunus* (close to 1800 samples) using SSR markers (17 for *Pyrus* and 24 for *Prunus* analyses). Regarding the *ex-situ* material, the genotyping for the collection of wild Apricot held by INRAE Bourdeaux was completed through Whole-Genome Sequencing (WGS). WGS for *in-situ* sample is on-going for *Malus*, *Pyrus* and *Prunus* (plum and apricot).

Phenotyping

Diversity and purity analysis identified the most suitable in-situ populations for the Genome-Environment Association analysis. Samples of the selected populations, including leaves, wood core,

petioles, and fruits, among others, have been evaluated following standardised protocols, and included in templates together with a given “plant anatomical entity code” for traceability. These templates are available in the sharepoint for data validation.

The phenotyping of the ex-situ collection is currently ongoing. Phenotypic data related to resilience, food and non-food uses, and fruit and leaves ‘omics’ are reported in MS 11.

All the plant metadata has been uploaded to the BIMS (Breeding Information Management System) and to the FruitDiv SharePoint.

3 Deviations or delays

3.1 Description/ reason (if applicable)

A delay has been encountered regarding the production of Whole-Genome Sequencing (WGS) data and the subsequent SNP calling. This deviation from the original timeline was necessary to accommodate the sampling of additional specimens during the second year of the project, ensuring a more robust and representative dataset for analysis.

3.2 Impact on other tasks (if applicable)

While this has postponed the final genomic characterisation of certain in-situ samples, the expanded sample size will significantly improve the accuracy of future analyses, such as those related to resilience and 'omics' reported in subsequent milestones.

3.3 Corrective actions to be taken to come back to schedule (if applicable)

No need for corrective action; this MS was placed well in advance to accommodate an extra year of sampling.

4 Annexes